

DIGITAL MARKETING - A CONCEPTUAL VIEW

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Abstract:

Digital marketing is a promotion of promotional products and services through digital media that lets both consumers and companies boost sales and profit. As the critical element among the marketing mix, the digital marketing is now considered to be a foremost factor in methods of sales and promotion. The major influence of advertisement is that it induces the customers wants and creates an impact to buy the products which can easily occur through audio and visual presentations. With the advancements in technology the promotion of the products gained major transformation through digital advertising. But such advancements in the economy faces more of supply than the demand. This makes a huge competition among marketers to promote their products or services. Hence this paper strives to explore and address the current issues and challenges faced in digital marketing.

Key Words: Digital Marketing, Interactivity, Advertising, Benefits

Introduction

In today's world, digital marketing has become a real phenomenon. And selling of such products and services is growing broader with the help of social media. It was launched in the 1990s and 2000s that obtained a massive market shift. Marketers are trying to maintain the regular contact that allows the better relationship of the client to build and sustain.

Digital marketing's main objective is through the exchange of goods towards the service sector, which mainly involves interactivity, connectivity and customer relationship building. In this transition, technological innovations, new channels and radical change in the media environment make it easier to challenge how consumers communicate with each other. Marketers are trying to keep in touch with their clients more often and this tends to increase the level of customer satisfaction and boost the flexibility and engagement required to help improve customer retention slowly. Our ultimate goal is to claim that being connected with customers will help achieve a positive customer satisfaction and loyalty reaction.

Consumers are presented with specific information and communication with products that can aid the consumer in their purchasing behaviour. This may include magazines, television, high and complex friend and peer interactions. For example: Nykaa try to keep in touch with the customers by sending email reminders with which they expect the customers to make up their purchasing mindset. Nykaa uses an appropriate database for collecting the purchase information to estimate the customer's behaviour at the time of purchase and provide a personalized email which encourages the buyers to consume the goods and services. By this technique Nykaa helps in selling out the goods and services effectively to their present customers and motivate new customers through introducing new trends in the market. With those ideas in mind, it cannot be shocking to see that the usage of such digital channels in the area of marketing has become a key point of developing new strategies for a number of companies.

Interactivity in the digital media is an effective tool helping out to obtaining customers opinion for searching information, feedback to get help. It also provides the customers to contribute the time more effectively with a brand they want to purchase and consume. Another importance of inter-activity helps in providing the marketer by effective information on customer's needs, requirements, wants, preferences, desire. Despite the trend in the usage of digital channels for the marketing sector for research and there are specific models which are considered for the explanations of the technology behind how often is digital marketing communication can effectively be a part in relationship of marketing, mainly for magnifying the customer satisfaction and trust. Plans can be obtained by various areas of marketing.

The ultimate proposal of this paper is to bring together the conceptual review for better study of how digital media marketing affects the customer trust and its challenges.

Definition of Digital Marketing:

The digital media helps in strengthening the relationship with the consumers and remove hindrance which can take place in future. The marketers need to identify the right chance of obtaining these digital marketing channels for maintaining proper touch and also for setting out the customers with cost-effective ways of purchasing. The main concept of "digital marketing" is to market the goods and services digitally and also to communicate with the customers through same channel wherein it can be used commercially, wherein the theoretical knowledge of digital media on how to use the different digital channels in present world.

Digital marketing uses digital platforms like internet ads or information related technology for extending and building the old traditional marketing to modern market. Digital marketing is being a mode accepted globally for the purpose of marketing and advertising. Digital marketing consists of the major four P's in the market which is product, price, place and promotion for customer attention and retention. Coviello, Milley and Marcolin also have defined e-marketing as "through the usage of network and other interactive technologies to create and mediate dialogue connecting the companies and recognized customers."

In the particular paper we refer digital marketing communication to be a communication with the help of channels and medium for a company or brand and its customers through digital media (e.g.: the internet, mail, smart phones, TV) and IT.

Review of Literature:

Digital marketing strategies are still growing across the world according to the headline global marketing index even a study proves that digital marketing tactics are approving hundred billion digital media helps the various brands to reach the customers through digital marketing talks about how it works in the market and shift in the products and services to the seller and buyers which involves one or more methods. Digital marketing started with instrument known as telegraphs in the 19th century. The bunch of acceptance for telegraphs, telephone, radio etc was very effective and high. Consumer accepted the change with complete heart and fulfilment. In current years businessmen are much relayed on digital media and marketing wherein they find out new and variant marketing strategies and techniques for the upbringing of the business. Digital marketing can be used as a multipurpose object in the world in of commerce. It performs different roles in the business sector to increase the sales and well as the profit of the firm. Digital marketing is seen as the best way of making money.

Digital marketing has come up with major changes in the traditional market it is highly dependent on technology and digital world it helps the business to grow and

survive in the marketing as it serves their customer in best possible manner by fulfilling their need and wants for the today's competitions. People in today's world are much exposed to digital marketing and social media. People almost spend their 3/4 day browsing online. The usage of digital marketing involves purchase, communication, search information about products, consume them and also communicate with others about their experience. The future of marketing will be happening through digital settings, especially through social media and mobiles in today's world consumers research about the product and services for consumption through digital plat forms. The main aim of digital marketing is interaction with customers about different brands etc.

The acceptance of digital marketing works through understanding the consumer's identity and self-concepts. Digital advertising is one of the important modes of marketing. Here the study is completely on the change in consumer behaviour and the way how customer gives feedback on different forms of advertisements and medias. In the past years' articles consider digital marketing from various point of view.

One of the most interesting perspective from few articles were based around how to tackle psychological reactance. The present article contributes to the understanding buy reviewing of the existing knowledge that is based on the exponent products and the dissimilar products which recommends the strategies for the marketing needs and activities. The main aim is to graph the significance of digitalisation of the marketer's. Digital marketing products are physically intangible in nature and also they cannot be touched. The position in digital marketing is with the comparison of the service and product elements.

Marketing has become an indispensable part of business which can never be ignored. In previous years businesses were carried out by traditional marketing. Examples flyers, magazine ads, newspaper, direct buying and selling through radio. Today's world is being ruled by Digital Marketing over Traditional marketing.

The topic talks about the usage of these dimensions like: intangibility, perishability, heterogeneity, simultaneous consumption (e.g. Zeithaml and Bitner 2000). Their potential for identifying services and goods has also been criticised by Ahtola (1985) and Gummesson (1995). However, the four dimensions can assist in analysing digital content. It is in that framework that they are employed here. As a group, digital products are positioned in the framework by the author koiso-kanttila (2002).

The essence of digital marketing is hard to enclose to specific discipline the similar material is dissipated across various journal. (Hanzon 2001) adopted a methodology which considered reinforcing trends in action. In recent days the demand for digital marketing has been introduced in hotel industry which is increasingly high with the adverse help of social media marketing includes work with networking sites and search engine services. The role of internet in the buying behaviour of tourist lead to modified in marketing plans which became increasingly digital. The study aims to identify how mangers of the hospitality industry use digital marketing as a marketing tool. The study had adopt a qualitative methodology comprising the analysis of the online presence of websites, Facebook, Twitter etc.

As digital marketing tools provides us with huge number of benefits to the hospitality industry whereas managers aren't concern about the future cause. Digital marketing is evolved with high performance. While globalisation makes going global and imperative, advances in information and communication technologies provide the means for taking business operations (Gray A. Knight 2007)

More companies are using digital marketing to reach their target customers with the increased use of digital media by consumers. Clarifying the intended meaning of other terminologies used throughout this paper is also helpful. Continuously emerging technologies present new opportunities and threats to business professionals, education and academic research (Buzzard, Crittenden & Mccarty, 2011; Hamill, Tagg, Stevenson & Vescovi, 2010; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Weiss, 2011). Business contact has revolutionized the use of social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter as legitimate business tools (levy & Birkner, 2011). A technology in current era aims to improve the visibility of website searches. The online marketing is in simple words SEO. For any small and large-scale business, SEO can be done. Often known as cost per click is PPC- PAY PER CLICK.

The transformation of communication channels is challenging for all industries in the digital era, but particularly for the communications and marketing sectors. As Mulhern (2009, p. 86) comments, media digitisation represents a phase-change in communications history. Kung (2008) argues that technical and customer behavioural changes have always been key drivers of shift in media strategy. In this study the word 'digital marketing skills' refers to the knowledge and awareness of digital marketing and its applications in the creative industries. The research strengthens connections between academia and industry, by "listening to the needs of marketers" (Reibstein, Day & Wind, 2009)

The digital marketing institute refers to digital marketing as "the use of digital technologies to create an integrated, targeted and measurable communication that helps to acquire and retain customers while building deeper relationships with them" (smith, 2007, in wymbys, 2011). Simply Digital Marketing (2012) defines the term as follows: ' Digital Marketing is a sub-sector of traditional marketing and uses modern digital channels for product placement, e.g. by customers and investors, of brands, products and business progress."The paper aims to enhance industry and academic knowledge of skills gaps across the communications industry and provide evidence-based model to help educators and practitioners address these gaps. Research strengthens academic-industrial connections by listening to marketers 'needs.'" (Reibstein, day, & wind, 2009,). The paper reviews existing literature that discusses industry-wide skill gaps and focuses more on the digital world. Research focuses more on social media that more describes marketing strategy. (Akar & Topcu, 2011; Brady et 2008) and research focuses more on developments in digital marketing. Integrating digital marketing skills is of great relevance for digital marketing in the long run. The biggest change in the development of information technology was the company encouraging opinion reviews of product services etc. which helps to create a wealthy marketing climate.

Field literature reveals a lack of research into the gaps in digital marketing skills in the communications industries. In their research, which focuses on social usage networking sites by Business 2 Business firms (Michaelidou and Siamagka 2011).

Identifying and developing skills that help in marketing highlights the idea of digital marketing skills in the industry that needs to be required for research to provide a relevant basis to meet media marketing's skill gaps. In the background of the industry some digital marketing skills are also needed Improving marketing approaches. Search engine optimization (SEO).mobile technology, consumer interaction and data analytics expertise to determine the efficacy of digital strategies among the most digital marketing capabilities.

The paper shows that the digital marketing are limited messaging platforms and social media resources due to deficiencies of technical skills. Even it involves analytical skills which measures and verifies digital approaches' effectiveness. The main concern is with strategic vision of the client.

Benefits of Using Digital Marketing:

Frequency:

The market communication and its focus on customer relationships have helped in gaining the attention of customers is been proved in the recent studies. The consequences justify that the strategies are mainly focused on brand communication through digital medium which has to be represented in a meaningful manner to encounter the brand and developing the consumer-brand and its relationships by seeking in additional sales help.

- **Information Processing:**

Customers are connected to the brand relationships which clarifies the buying and consuming behaviour of the customers through the process, and also maintain a very healthy balance connecting the comprehensive consistency and the psychological requirements. Hence the process helps in increasing frequency of customers towards brand communication. Repetition of purchase and sales has a main impact on the customer trust and satisfaction. Digital media helps acquiring and improving practical experiences with particular brand and to search for information about possible brands.

- **Personalized Communication:**

The communication done through personalization is a customized form of advertising done to communicate with the customers effectively by gaining the customers trust and loyalty by providing much personal services. The ultimate aim is to indentify divergent customers and provide personalized messages for customer's needs. Thus, the marketing communication would have the potential for a better result on increasing sales which is required for customer loyalty related to the situation. The logic of personalization is been identified in the studies earlier through the mode of advertising, that helps in revealing the relevance in personal messages. Individual try spending a lot of time in the processing stage of personalisation. Personalisation leads to more product and service relevance thoughts. This method helps the firm in creating a verbal and virtual commitment with the customers.

- **Interactive Brand:**

The platform helps in providing way more opportunities in changing the form of communication from one way to another which is been an interactive session for the customers and also provide them with relevant information about the goods. Wherein the customers has an easy access to networks which can be sued for search and support, later filter out the relevant information they require. By this technique digital marketing as an effective provider of service sector.

The different form of interactivity can be learned from the following: The Functional view concerns function of an alliance (e.g.: response) characteristics (e.g.: verbal), elements (e.g.: requirement of control), procedure and output (e.g.: consumer satisfaction). These functional elements can differ, consisting on the channels and media being convinced.

Mediating Factors:

Another key function in the model of communication and digital media which highly require personalisation and response which helps in analysing how customer loyalty affects the digital media.

An Integrative Model of the Effects of Digital Marketing Communication on Customer Loyalty

Source: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>

• **Customer Characteristics:**

Each customer differs from one another. Hence the response to Digital Marketing will not be same by each individual customer or willing to engage in it. It helps the company to understand the customers future potential and also the worth on investment in extensive communication and building good relationships.

The Secret Marketing Process:

Source: <https://www.responsify.com/>

Digital marketing communication can help advertisers boost their promotion and productivity returns when the prevailing marketing paradigm moves from exchange of goods to service. Online networks offer makers cost-effective ways to keep in touch with consumers regularly and boost customer loyalty. With such a prospective mind, it is not surprising that many companies are making use of digital channels in marketing an essential part of their strategy.

This paper will suggest that brand contact helps to build consumer trust and loyalty by regular interaction and comparable subject matter. Another way to generate market loyalty and its relationship is by using brand contact to process information that holds consumers faithful to the brand. Increasing these improves behavioural customer relationships.

Personalized and engaging helps to build brand loyalty by creating effective communication with customers. As an appropriate arbitrator for digital marketing, the other features involved in customer engagement and partnership variables function. The number of models being created is complex in nature which affects the relationship of customers among them. The analysis would be successful if the experiment were carried out in two or more directions before the entire model assesses the test. And the application of digital marketing are thus found in the following aspects as an advertising medium is must for digital marketing, a direct response medium, as a lead-generation method, an effective distribution channel, support for sales transaction platform, serves as good customer service mechanism, reflects as better relationship building medium.

In social media marketing, public relations, display advertising, internet marketing, email marketing, SEO, PPC, content marketing, digital marketing is used. The good news about digital marketing is, it can continue on a very small scale. All you need to become a digital marketing specialist is an Internet connection, a computer and a small amount of money. Easy to master digital marketing by incorporating the principles within your own mini project.

Conclusion:

The paper conceptualizes the benefits and the working of digital marketing. The reviews provides the view to analyse the trends in digital marketing strategies as perceived by customers. Consumers always have an urge to buy new products, with the changes in socio-economic aspect such as increasing percentage of nuclear families and thereby creates more need. To sustain in the market, the marketers are suppose to identify and produce new products over time. Also the study address the importance of choosing prompt strategies to sustain their market in huge competition.

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